

OPERAS-P

OPEN SCHOLARLY COMMUNICATION IN THE EUROPEAN
RESEARCH AREA FOR SSH - PREPARATION

WP6 Innovation

**D6.3 Report on innovative approach to SSH
FAIR data and publications**

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DRAFT

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- PREPARATION

Deliverable 6.3

Report on innovative approach to SSH FAIR data and publication

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I. Executive summary and objectives

The FAIR principles¹ (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability) are a set of foundational guidelines aiming at improving the management of digital scholarly resources, for both humans and machines. Considering digital objects as a whole, focusing on data management and reuse, and allowing for cross-disciplinary research, the FAIR principles provide an innovative approach for the Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) practices. More fragmented, less data-centric, and in some fields dealing with physical objects, the SSH environment still needs some guidance to fully exploit the potentialities of the FAIR principles. A major component for the integration into the [European Open Science Cloud](#) (EOSC), the FAIR principles are also, more broadly, an important tool for open science.

Therefore, OPERAS-P Task 6.3 aimed at providing the knowledge base and the view of the community in finding the most suitable way to make the FAIRification of SSH data possible, with a threefold approach:

- **Speak the same language:** the first step was focusing on different kinds of data in SSH and issues in implementing FAIR principles, via a thorough review of the rich and growing literature about data in SSH.
- **Work with the community:** through focus groups and workshops, stakeholders were engaged to find out the perception about FAIR data, the needs of different communities, the challenges of FAIRification with regards to different disciplines.
- **Showing the road ahead:** based on the review and workshops, some suggestions to entail the directions for OPERAS concerning the FAIRification of data can be proposed, including FAIRification tools prototypes, as well as measures to further engage the community both in discussions and implementation.

The same structure is maintained below, in reporting about the main activities and findings.

The task 6.3 worked in synergy with the parallel activities carried out by the [CO-OPERAS](#) Implementation Network (IN) within the [GOFAIR](#) initiative, aimed at the FAIRification of SSH data, including publications.

The task was impacted by the pandemic situation, as it became more difficult to engage with the community in fully interactive and informal virtual focus groups. The collective activities were, therefore, more limited during 2020, but there are already plans for a new series of workshops to be held in 2021 second semester.

¹ The FAIR principles are fully described on the GOFAIR website: <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/>

II. Speaking the same language

According to the European Commission's *Turning FAIR into reality* 2018 report², the first FAIRification step for research communities is to “define how the FAIR principles and related concepts apply in their context”, especially with regard to “data types”. With this recommendation in mind, a literature review has been conducted to investigate the definition of data in the SSH context. The analyzed corpus consists of 28 English and French open access publications all published, with one exception, after 2008. The literature review helped first to examine the notion of data at a general level, considering its rather recent generalization in the SSH. The literature also allowed us to focus on the concrete expressions of data in the SSH context, specifically in Digital Humanities (DH) disciplines, and to indicate some pathways for a flexible and comprehensive FAIRification of SSH data.

A. Data definitions

A simple glimpse at the literature confirms a paradox that anybody, nowadays, can notice: while being used always more broadly, in research and beyond, the term “data” does not correspond to a single and shared definition. In the research area, more particularly, data universalism is a characteristic of the new “data-centric” paradigm. In that sense, one could wonder if defining data is not bound to be a delusion and if it does even matter. However, such a universalism comes with limitations proper to any universalism: it can be applied anywhere, it does not perfectly apply everywhere. The literature review happens to show that a definitional effort could indeed be useful and bring, after some clarifications, specific indications for the FAIRification of SSH data.

At a conceptual level, data has both an epistemological and a technological meaning, which can be related to specific historical periods. In “Data before the Fact” (Gitelman et al., 2013), D. Rosenberg reminds that the data concept is closely linked to the 17th century’s scientific revolution, and thus to the very nature of the Modern Era. Bacon was writing in Latin and never used the term “data”, but his scientific method precisely contains the concept: his lists of categorized observations from which rules can be inferred correspond to what we would call today data collection, cleaning, and analysis. The scientific argument thus starts from an entity that is, as Rosenberg says, “beyond argument”: the data. As such, data appears to be essential to the definition of modern empirical science, which progressively became almost a synonym of Western modern

² *Turning FAIR into reality*, 2018, https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/info/files/turning_fair_into_reality_1.pdf

science. Proper to science and distinct from the fact or the evidence, data gained in this historical stage its first quality, the transparency, but not yet the universality.

As noted by D. Rosenberg, data still had in this stage a limited usage. It acquired its new universal quality with the digital turn. The intersection between information science and technology has changed the status and the meaning of data: anything that can be transposed into binary bits constitutes data that in turn feeds and supports the entire digital environment. At first strictly scientific as a concept and a practice, data became informational, with a wider meaning now ranging from knowledge to technology. To put it simply: empirical science had data, the digital environment is data. This implied a change of scale and nature with the notion of big data, “created and defined by industry, media and academia alike” (Schöch, 2013). More specifically, in the scientific field, big data now relies on the idea that “correlation supersedes causation, and science can advance even without coherent models” (Anderson, 2008). In this stage also, the concept of data appears to crystallize an epistemological major shift: the evolution from empirical induction to neural connection corresponds to the evolution from scientific to informational data, now typical of the Digital Era.

B. SSH Data and the FAIR Principles

The epistemological and technological nature of the data concept, as well as its transparent and universal qualities, are challenging, and indeed are sometimes challenged, in the SSH area. Such challenges appear clearly in the very title of a 2013 book: *Raw data is an oxymoron* (Gitelman et al., 2013). The book furthered the discussion launched by J. Drucker (2011), who proposed to use the term *capta*, “taken”, instead of data, “given”, in order to highlight that knowledge is situated and constructed. SSH materials are indeed “semiotic systems [...] which depend on semantics and pragmatics” (García-Peñalvo, 2016), requiring interpretation for their usage and comprehension. From a methodological point of view, “very little humanities research is based on a single form or source of knowledge, with corroboration or triangulation between sources being more the norm” (Edmond, 2020). From a typological point of view, instead of generic data, SSH use “precise terminology (e.g., primary sources, secondary sources, theoretical documents, bibliographies, critical editions, annotations, notes, etc.)” (Edmond & Tóth-Czifra, 2018). This typological specificity also has legal implications, for publications and cultural heritage fall under specific legal provisions, while data as such does not exist as a legal object. Moreover, SSH materials are often “analog, non-discrete data, which cannot be analyzed or transformed computationally” (García-Peñalvo, 2016). If this does not mean that such objects cannot be digitally transposed and referenced, their integration into the digital

environment often corresponds to over-simplifying models.

Alongside more traditional practices, the SSH area has also seen the development of the Digital Humanities field. This field can rely on the same traditional objects, but integrating and processing them in the digital environment, for instance by “mining data from historical documents” (Posner, 2015). It can also create new scientific objects, considering that they all have in common the “encoding in the form of numbers, which allows a machine to read and execute sequential actions on this information” (Ollion and Boelaert, 2015). This generic approach represents an adaptation of the big data notion, for “these data can be ‘massive’ or not, born-digital or not, open access or proprietary” (ibid.). Allowing to reshape the definition of data, and therefore of disciplines’ boundaries as well, the DH field somehow perpetuates the SSH specificity by dealing with a high variety of data.

Empirical and informational data are now fused in the common area of what is sometimes called “technoscience”³, i.e., the combination of modern scientific methods and technological innovations. This opens a new perspective: every informational data is technically data, every data can potentially be also scientific data, even if not always immediately. Offering guidance for the management of such generic data, the FAIR principles represent a potential common framework for this new perspective, and somehow the universal access key to the masses of existing data. In that prospect, the general “datafication” process can be understood as part of an ecosystem that connects not only research and technology but also economy. Considering the variety of parties involved, De Mauro et al. (2016) coined this definition of big data: “the Information asset characterized by such a High Volume, Velocity and Variety to require specific Technology and Analytical Methods for its transformation into Value”. This definition is often referred to as the “3 V’s” definition of big data, not noticing that there is an additional V to its very end: Value, a synonym for both scientific relevance and financial value. The FAIR principles undoubtedly increase the data management’s sustainability, as well as the visibility of a wider range of scientific objects, but a broader perspective should not minimize the questions raised about who will shape the model of data expected and accepted, and collect the added-value of the FAIRified data in the end.

This general overview lets us better understand the status and situation of SSH data in the current ecosystem if it does not provide a final definition of data, especially in the

³ See: <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Technoscience>. The term is used here with a descriptive meaning, but its precise definition is still discussed. It can have a more critical value, related to the works of J. Habermas, where the combination of science and technology is considered as an ideology (P. Mounier, 2018).

heterogeneous context of SSH. It leads however to consider more properly the recommendations from the aforementioned *Turning FAIR into reality* report: the definitional effort is less conceptual than contextual. It should concern digital objects in the prospect of their FAIRification, relying on priorities and feasibility parameters, assessed by the data producers and managers, according to specific, maybe distinct, objectives. In a 2017 report, Schöpfel et al. propose a pragmatic view distinguishing essentially source and result data. The distinction generally allows to separate, even within the SSH, the “data used by researchers for their research” and the “data produced as research results”. This conception of data might allow us to move from a definition of data based on data types and disciplines to the management of objects related to specific communities and aims. Another convergent suggestion is to identify, within the existing and well-rooted SSH practices, a FAIRification that pre-existed FAIR principles. A general recommendation would then be to accurately address data’s multiple dimensions, rather than its genericity, by taking into account the dynamics (sources, enrichments, and outputs) and the finality (storage, analysis, and dissemination). Such a perspective opens a field of probably demanding, but rich and fruitful collaborations between SSH infrastructures and networks.

III. Working with the community

A. Workshops

1. National and international workshops

Complementing the literature review with the objective of gathering feedback and suggestions from the research community about the FAIRification of SSH data, a series of workshops was organized.

National workshops thus took place in different countries: Italy (Turin, September 2019), Portugal (Coimbra, December 2019), Germany (Göttingen, January 2020), France (Paris, February 2020). By choice, these four workshops were held in national languages both to ease the discussion and to stay more anchored to local issues and practices. The series started and ended with two international workshops. In Porto in September 2019, at the Open Science Fair, a workshop allowed to address broadly the topic of FAIR SSH. In conclusion of the series, a final international workshop was held in Brussels in March 2020, in order to elaborate recommendations from the outcomes of the whole series.

The workshops were organized in collaboration with the CO-OPERAS IN and through the support of OPERAS partners: University of Turin, University of Coimbra, and the

Huma-Num RI. The Göttingen workshop was jointly organized with DARIAH ERIC and the H2020 project [SSHOC](#) (Social Sciences and Humanities Open Cloud), which is currently building a data and services cluster for the SSH. Besides discussing with the participants their needs and experiences with the FAIR principles in their research, this workshop also aimed at receiving feedback about the conception of the SSHOC Open Marketplace.

Each national workshop followed the same structure in order to facilitate the comparison of the outcomes and prepare the final international workshop. After a presentation of the OPERAS RI and of the CO-OPERAS IN, the key concepts related to FAIR were presented to the audience. The workshop consisted of two collaborative sessions: the first one, to define data in the SSH according to each participant's experience and discipline; the second one, to assess with the participants the current FAIRness of their outputs and tools.

We reached 76 participants from more than 20 different research areas (see Annex C), going from archaeology to economics, from hindology to librarianship. The audience consisted mainly of researchers and Ph.D. candidates, but technical experts also attended the workshops. The participants' experience with FAIR principles varied likewise.

Before engaging the research community in FAIR implementations, the first goal of the workshops was to inform about the content and purpose of the FAIR principles, and, as a matter of fact, many participants did not have extensive knowledge of the principles. The format chosen for the workshops precisely allowed us to progressively introduce the FAIR principles, by starting the discussion from the researchers' data and related practices. The workshops then helped to identify the challenges regarding the applicability of FAIR principles in the SSH, to test and assess the uses of the principles by the researchers, and to make suggestions regarding FAIR.

2. Discussing the specificities of SSH data

As mentioned before, the first aim of the workshops was to define data in the context of the SSH. It was possible to reach a certain consensus on some aspects. Ironically, the first of them is that there is no consensus on what data is since the understanding of data depends on the discipline or area, and hence, no cross-disciplinary definition is possible. Some participants even showed a sort of reluctance toward the term "data", preferring to use the term "record". Other participants consider that their work, rather than relying on data, consists of using texts, images, archives, etc.

The consensual idea that the definition of data depends on a given context is also key. In other words, it is necessary to take into account the context and methods of data

production. In the SSH, besides the discipline, the specific theory, methodology, and technical apparatus are significant if not determinant to the production of data. Furthermore, data is usually considered as a construct resulting from researcher's interpretation and subjectivity. As a consequence, according to the participants, the idea of raw data does not make much sense in the SSH.

Throughout this series of workshops, the discussion evolved from an attempt at a broader definition of data in the SSH to more specific discussions that focused on the specific challenges faced by the various disciplines and on different practical aspects. Such discussions illustrated, through detailed use cases, some of the specificities of SSH data, and more precisely the complexity of "datafication" in this field. Regardless of the nature of the data, the SSH disciplines present a variety of technical, legal, and organizational challenges. From an institutional point of view, the participants generally agreed to stress the lack of incentives to share data, the lack of recognition for the work of data handling, which discourage researchers to share and maintain their data for reuse, and the lack of training on how to use repositories.

The second part of the workshops focused on FAIR principles, the challenges its implementation entails, the manners in which it is already put into practice, and some possible recommendations on its use.

According to the participants, the FAIR principles implementation requires a cultural change, since not all the SSH communities have moved toward the new, data-centric paradigm. As mentioned earlier, researchers may not recognize "data" in their field. The research environment remains generally competitive, and, in some cases, the SSH research may be less collaborative and more single-authored, with a weaker tradition of openly sharing data as a consequence.

In the same way, publishing in open access journals is not the first choice yet and, according to various participants, print culture continues to prevail. In their minds, publishing practices, even in the digital context, have kept the limited dissemination and accessibility that characterized the print era. In that sense, the view on scholarly communication would also benefit from a cultural shift. In other words, instead of limiting the scholarly communication to the publication of a paper (as an end goal), a complementary - and FAIR - effort should be made, along the whole research process, in order to take care of everything used to write the paper, especially the data.

Finally, in some cases, technical aspects do not appear to be the major issue, since

researchers have been using FAIR tools as TEI (the Text Encoding Initiative⁴) in various areas. Therefore, finding the right advocacy strategy is the key. Emphasizing the practical benefits of FAIR for researchers and their communities, presenting good examples and successful use cases seems necessary. At the same time, the participants outlined the necessity to preserve the tradition of SSH by finding the right balance between protecting the specificities of the field and adopting the standards necessary to integrate them into a wider context, such as the EOSC. One of the SSH specificities regards multilingualism because the domain is often anchored in national or regional contexts and produces outputs in other languages than English. The FAIR maturity model created with the Research Data Alliance ([RDA](#)) starts to be widely used: it relies on a set of automated FAIR metrics that might become an important part of the integration of data within the EOSC. This entails, therefore, defining assessment criteria that take into account specificities of the research in the SSH domain.

When considering more specifically the application of each of the FAIR principles, the participants identified various lacks or insufficiencies.

The workshops led to a series of interesting observations regarding **Findability**: there is often insufficient knowledge and use of FAIR practices (digital skills), or a lack of FAIR tools in specific disciplines or contexts (repositories, thesauri, authority files), and sometimes a lack of coordination between FAIR services (indexes, unique identifiers, standards). This ends up with low-quality, inconsistent, and hardly searchable metadata. Moreover, the diversity of outputs characteristic of the SSH is not well-represented in discovery systems. This relates with the types of data used in the SSH, but also to their nature, as some disciplines deal with physical objects. As the funding goes more and more to digital collections, libraries may not invest enough in the management and preservation of such physical objects.

As for **Accessibility**, some of the difficulties mentioned are related to the lack of a single database (data are fragmented in several sources). Moreover, specific problems appear related to the type of data (texts digitized as images are not searchable). More often than not, the data is discoverable but lacks the essential information about the specific software necessary to read it.

⁴ “The Text Encoding Initiative (TEI) is a consortium which collectively develops and maintains a standard for the representation of texts in digital form” ([Text Encoding Initiative](#)). The consortium produces a set of Guidelines which defines hundreds of different concepts and the rules for how to combine them. The TEI Guidelines specifies encoding methods for machine-readable texts, mostly in social sciences, humanities, and linguistics.

Interoperability is also hindered because metadata schemas, methods, and tools, are often strictly tailored and linked to specific projects, instead of adopting standard schemas or formats. Furthermore, as datasets, especially when established from born-digital sources like social networks, may have many layers, interoperability becomes even more complex.

Finally, although the challenges concerning **Reusability** may be presented as being related to the lack of provenance details or documentation, they seem mostly related to difficulties with legal aspects. A very significant difficulty regards copyright. It may vary according to the country and it is not always easy to identify who has proprietary rights, especially in particular cases like multilayered corpora. Another commonly identified problem is linked to lack of clear licensing statements, lack of licenses associated with specific objects such as databases, lack of skills to associate the appropriate license to an object. There are also difficulties regarding the specificities of SSH data, among them, the lack of knowledge of the existing laws regulating the usage of archives, personal data, or images and text owned by third parties. The participants acknowledge the need to reflect more on the implications of FAIR principles when dealing with any of these issues.

Despite all these limitations, the workshops also confirmed that some FAIR components are already part of researchers' practices. Some researchers use persistent identifiers such as DOIs or ORCID. Also, TEI has been in place for a while and ensures a certain level of interoperability. In addition, institutions and researchers offer training, for Ph.D. or even Master students, focusing on the search, creation, and exploration of databases, on digital literacy programs and policies.

3. Suggestions for the SSH FAIRification

A final result of the workshops was the production of a set of suggestions of FAIR application in the SSH. They can be clustered around the following topics:

- **SSH specificities:**
 - Field traditions should be preserved.
 - Improving referencing and discovery of multilingual content .
- **Governance:**
 - SSH Research Infrastructure should be research-driven to be responsive to the researchers' needs.
- **Architecture:**

- An easy-to-use environment in which researchers seamlessly practice open science should be provided.
- It is also crucial to provide a single point of access to publications and data with an efficient filtering system (examples of the TRIPLE and the SSHOC projects).
- Indices need to be available via a regular web search, to improve findability.
- Bibliodiversity (considering the variety of publishing types, languages, and business models⁵) should be fostered.
- **Standards and metadata:**
 - Metadata guidelines should be produced, both at the discipline level and at the general level, increasing the overall metadata quality and the multi-disciplinary uses.
 - A minimum set of metadata to integrate/expand to share at least a common layer should be established
 - Methods need to be standardized so they can be univocally recalled.
- **Tools:**
 - Build a tools registry to provide updated and exhaustive information about existing FAIR tools.
 - Ensuring the sustainability of services and tools is crucial to create an actual FAIR ecosystem.
- **Training and skills:**
 - More training related to Digital Humanities, in general, is needed.
 - More training on a wider and more detailed range of data/metadata skills should be offered.
 - Data and metadata skills should be included in curricula at an early stage as well as questions on data management, tools, licenses.
 - Data sharing should be addressed already during the design phase of the research.

⁵ See: <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Bibliodiversity>.

B. Outreach

1. TRIPLE kick-off meeting Dec. 2019

The work carried out on FAIR data was briefly presented during the TRIPLE project kick-off meeting in Paris, in December 2019. TRIPLE (Transforming Research through Innovative Practices for Linked Interdisciplinary Exploration) is an innovative multilingual and multicultural discovery solution for the SSH that will be the OPERAS Discovery service.

FAIR data are crucial to enable a common point of access to SSH literature, data, and research material in general. Hence, the presentation of the then ongoing workshops and the preliminary reflections of the communities got very positive feedback from the attendants.

2. Berlin Open Science conference Mar. 2020

The results of the workshops organized in synergy with Co-OPERAS were presented during the Berlin Open Science conference, on March 8, 2020.

The presentation was a synoptic view of the results of the workshops and the ALLEA Report Sustainable and FAIR Data Sharing in the Humanities⁶ and was co-authored by an ALLEA member.

It was clear the perfect consonance among some issues raised by the researchers attending the workshops and the issues tackled by the Recommendations included in the ALLEA Report, first of all, the importance of defining data. To be Findable, the need for metadata standards was identified as crucial; to be Accessible, it's clear the need for a trusted repository and a discovery tool like the one OPERAS is building via the TRIPLE project; to be Interoperable, the community should build ontologies and be more visible in the FAIRsharing registry; to be Reusable, more advice and skills on copyright and licenses are needed.

3. OPERAS Conference Nov. 2020

CO-OPERAS IN has participated in the OPERAS conference "Opening up Social Sciences and Humanities in Europe: From Promises to Reality". This conference promoted the debate about the future perspectives for the SSH and its shift towards openness

⁶ Sustainable and FAIR Data Sharing in the Humanities, ALLEA Report 2020, <https://doi.org/10.7486/DRI.tq582c863>

regarding the role of research infrastructures, services and policies, researchers' needs and challenges to be overcome.

As part of this conference, CO-OPERAS co-organized a workshop with the EOSC Secretariat, the DARIAH ERIC, the SSHOC project, and the National Library of Belgium (KBR). Being a component of the EOSC co-creation process, the workshop's subject was: "[Anticipating the future of research in the social sciences and humanities](#)". The organizers' presentations allowed connecting the actions currently led by the SSH projects and ERICs and the changes to be expected in research practices within the next ten years, with a particular focus on FAIRification. The participants were then invited to discuss more specifically the evolutions, either required or wished, in terms of skills and impact in the SSH field.

Regarding skills, the participants addressed the specific complexity of data in the SSH (for example, corpora vs datasets), the different actors (such as IT support and SSH researchers), and the kind of service expected (that should be discipline-specific). Scientists should develop their understanding of the data lifecycle. Some of the services needed include translation challenges (especially with the increasing amount of content in Chinese), collaboration with infrastructures outside the European area, corpus alignment, among others. As for impact, the discussions outlined, both the value of humanities research to solve societal challenges and the improvement of the human-computer interface by extended use of natural language.

4. GOFAIR Convergence Symposium Dec. 2020

During the International GOFAIR Convergence Symposium, CO-OPERAS furthered the debate about the FAIR continuum for the SSH data and publications. As the goal of CO-OPERAS is to develop a friendly ecosystem aligned with FAIR principles and such an ecosystem does not exist yet, the conference aimed at receiving contributions to its construction. The discussion brought to the center of the scene the relation between FAIR and multiple aspects, such as education, infrastructure, data curation, policies, and open science. More precisely, the workshop stemmed from the EOSC pilot on skills and capabilities⁷ to identify the specific role in FAIRification for each of the functions listed by the EOSC pilot report: researchers, data scientists, data advisors, and data managers. In that sense, the workshop was an attempt to represent the landscape of required collaborations for the building of an SSH FAIR continuum.

⁷ <https://eoscpilot.eu/content/d75-strategy-sustainable-development-skills-and-capabilities>.

5. OPERAS-P WP6 conference, Feb. 2021

Like the other tasks of the Work Package of OPERAS-P about scholarly communication innovations, the task on FAIR SSH presented some of its outcomes during the event on “The future of scholarly communication” organized by IBL-PAN, the WP leader. Through the presentation of the literature review on data definition in the SSH and the provisional FAIR publishing toolkit⁸, it was possible to investigate with the community the following topic: “Publications as data”. The outcomes have been first discussed by a panel of experts⁹ and then with the audience.

The experts confirmed the uncertain status of data in general, as it constitutes a “boundary language object” more fit for computer science than for information science. In the SSH, in particular, the hybrid landscape (both digital and non-digital) and the importance of publications, with their specific legal status, makes it difficult to apply the concept of data uniformly. Therefore, the suggestion was to start the FAIRification process from the existing practices and identify potential convergences with the generic FAIR principles. The experts also stressed the importance of the broader context in which the FAIRification and the related “datafication” take place. Although established by the research community, the FAIR principles implementation puts some pressure on non-industrial actors handling legacy data, like in the case of some open access publishing platforms. In that prospect, it seems crucial that the FAIRification process is not conducted according to a top-down approach, but is focused instead, for both SSH researchers and publishing platforms, on the actual finality and benefit of the FAIR principles implementation.

IV. Showing the road ahead

A. Advocacy

Advocacy on FAIR data must be one of the paths ahead, as it was clear from the researchers attending the workshops that the concept is still almost obscure. Not only there is generally low awareness of what “FAIR” means, but there are also some misconceptions about it. The most common ones are the idea that FAIR are standards for the hard sciences, so they cannot apply to Humanities, and that “A”, Accessible, stands for

⁸ See subsection “Guidance” below.

⁹ We thank here again our three panelists: Jennifer Edmond (DARIAH), Émilie Paquin (Érudit), and Joachim Schöpfel (University of Lille). Their insights were very useful and some of them were directly integrated in the summaries of this document; others helped us to formulate the final recommendations.

“Open”, generating concerns towards “openness” especially in cases of sensitive data. It is important to stress that FAIR are principles and the first recommendation of the already mentioned Turning FAIR into reality report is “Define FAIR for implementation”. Humanities need to adapt the FAIR principles to their specific way of conducting and publishing research if they want to be part of EOSC.

In order to achieve this goal, in synergy with the OPERAS Special Interest Group (SIG) on Advocacy, a set of cards containing and contextualizing the abovementioned ALLEA Report recommendations and the workshops' outputs are being produced, starting in March 2021.

The target is to convey the message that FAIR data matters to the composite research community in the SSH, adapting and suggesting existing tools to ease the adoption of good practices. The idea is to extrapolate from the recommendations at the end of each ALLEA report chapter some sentences, and translate them into practical advice or connect them to already existing tools, standards, communities of practice.

It should result in printable “cards”, deposited in Zenodo, for the community to be used in training, workshops, and focus groups. The inspiring model is the Myths on FAIR webpage created by the Danish e-infrastructure Cooperation (DeiC). Particular attention will be paid to graphics, to create an appealing output.

B. Guidance

In order to pave the way for actual FAIRification of the SSH, the task also intended to prototype FAIRification tools useful for the community. The first one is a FAIR publishing toolkit, as the literature review and the workshops confirmed the importance of publications in the SSH area. The second one, which will have to be refined and finalized together with the community, stems from the Implementation Profiles methodology suggested by GOFAIR.

1. FAIR publishing toolkit prototype

It is widely acknowledged that the services providing data, such as publishing systems, should themselves be FAIR-compliant; nevertheless, the literature regarding data services other than data repositories is scarce. A digital infrastructure for open scholarly communication in the SSH, OpenEdition carried out an internal full review to assess the degree of FAIRness of its activities. A task force performed the assessment and, as a result, made specific recommendations to apply FAIR principles to the organisation's activities. This assessment process led to the development of a provisional FAIR

Publishing Toolkit to offer guidance for the FAIRification of publishing services.

a) Methodology

While they are similar to data repositories to some extent, publishing systems present two main differences when compared to them: the type of activities and the type of customers. A publishing system can be seen as the “datafication” unit of textual contents, making these contents appropriately available for the digital environment, standardising not only the metadata but also, in some cases, the data itself. Regarding the type of customers, a publishing service addresses firstly the needs of publishers and of the authors, and also the needs of the end-users, the readers. The FAIR review conducted here had to take into account such specificities.

The FAIR review methodology used in this project presented three main phases: preparation, assessment, and result phase, which produced the list of recommendations for the FAIR principles implementation, according to objectives and priorities.

b) Preparation phase: Context and challenges

The preparation phase gathered the available information to define the perimeter of the FAIR review. It comprised two steps. The landscape study provided definitions and established the relationship between FAIR and Open Science, Linked Open Data and Plan S. The real use cases allowed the team to draw a list of potential service improvements that could be achieved by implementing FAIR principles.

c) Assessment phase: The FAIR principles as a grid

The assessment phase consists of four steps described below.

Contextualized FAIR principles

A review of each FAIR principle allowed to translate them for the publishing context and to operate the first adjustments to the data-centric FAIR principles. The main adjustments of the findability principles regard the contextual and technical aspects related mostly to persistent identifiers. Accessibility is one primary goal of open access publishing, with restricted access being the exception. Interoperability is generally addressed, at least for traditional contents like journals and books, through the use of interoperable standards both for the data (TEI) and the metadata (DublinCore, METS, MODS). For less traditional content like blogs and scientific events, the level of interoperability is significantly lower.

Reusability appears to be the less clarified principle, given the variety of legal provisions applying to digital publications and their contents.

Data definition

The second step of the FAIR assessment consisted of the definition of the datasets to analyse. In the case of OpenEdition, the first series of datasets is naturally related to the four platforms of dissemination: OpenEdition Journals, OpenEdition books, Hypothèses, and Calenda. However, a publishing system generates and processes other datasets, which can be related to added-value services or the information system monitoring (vocabularies, training corpus, metrics, catalogues).

FAIR maturity full assessment

The third step of the FAIR assessment process was the full analytical review of each dataset according to the FAIR principles. The general FAIRness of OpenEdition's publishing system is very uneven and hindered by contextual aspects, and by the non-traditional typologies of publishing as well. This full review showed the main areas where FAIRness could be improved and those that required more detailed information to formulate more accurate recommendations.

Focused assessments

The FAIRness full assessment led to the state-of-the-art of some fundamental elements for the implementation of FAIR principles. These elements are persistent identifiers (definition, different types), licensing issues (regarding data and scholarly publication legal status), and the management of authors' information.

d) Result phase: Recommendations

The priority recommendations regard persistent identifiers and licensing. For PIDs it is to implement Handles for all the data of the system; keep the Crossref DOIs where they exist; expand the coverage of DOIs through Datacite DOIs. As for licensing, the recommendation is two-fold: establish a policy at the level of the organization; accompany the publishers and authors in the adoption of open licenses. Additionally, the information about licensing should be better integrated with the information system. The extended objectives focus on author's information management (update of the information system to

have the capacity to manage structured information about the authors), controlled vocabularies (description of their provenance and their content), machine-actionability (relation with the accessibility to the contents by the machines), and Data Management Plan (adoption of a Data Management Plan as a continuation and an improvement of this documentation effort).

This work confirmed that, if the FAIR principles are generic, their implementation is contextual. This is particularly true in the case of a service which deals with a variety of objects and operates in a complex environment. The FAIRification of a publishing service requires actions related both to the sustainability of the information system and to the quality of the service for the customers. As a process where specific steps and priorities are identified, the FAIRification is not a one-stand action, and the implementation of FAIR principles has also to consider a long-term perspective by fully integrating the principles to the service's general management. The provisional toolkit for the FAIRification of publishing services is entering into a process to be validated, improved, and enriched by the community to ensure it fully addresses the specific needs of the publishing services in terms of FAIRification.

2. Drafting SSH Implementation profiles

In order to provide guidance to the various research communities, GOFAIR has set up an analytical grid able to establish Implementation Profiles (IPs). Similar to the grid used in the FAIR publishing toolkit, the IP grid presents the full list of detailed FAIR principles as a questionnaire allowing to specify the existing FAIR implementations both for data and for metadata. The objective is to obtain a list of resources (software, standards, protocols, etc.) enabling FAIR and already in use. The grid is filled by a specific research community (gathered around a discipline, a project, an object, etc.) and thus defines the FAIR Implementation Profile of the community. The comparison between the various IPs makes it then possible to identify existing similarities and potential convergences between communities.

Given the variety of the SSH area in itself, the IP appears to be an efficient tool to bring collectively the SSH into a shared FAIR ecosystem. The flexibility of the IP model will allow to define IPs based on a discipline, or an object (book, article, audio/video files, etc.), taking into account the multidisciplinary aspect of SSH research. The existing GOFAIR IP model, although based on the generic FAIR principles, contains some expert indications and example suggestions that needed to be adapted for the SSH broader community. A first and adapted IP model has therefore been presented during the GOFAIR 2020

Symposium in order to collect feedback on the model. With the support of the CO-OPERAS IN, the model can be further refined and completed in the future through focus groups representing the SSH various communities.

3. Networking

Alongside advocacy and guidance, the FAIRification of SSH also requires the direct involvement of the data and publications producers. As emerged during the workshops, the lack of actual incentives for FAIR implementations hinders the generalization of FAIR practices. Furthermore, it is important that the advantages appear clearly to the producers, and do not seem a top-down recommendation. For these reasons, it seemed useful to suggest the creation of a dissemination space able to make visible FAIR achievements and their utility.

The suggestion led first to a quick landscape analysis able to assess the possibility to create a journal dedicated to the FAIRification of the SSH: it would both increase the dissemination of the FAIR outputs and reward the producers of such outputs. The landscape analysis showed that the topic was not addressed fully or directly by existing journals, however, it also outlined that the editorial project could be better defined thanks to the engagement of researchers. In order to prepare the creation of the FAIR SSH journal, it has therefore been decided to create a blog that will facilitate the emergence of a community of interest around this topic of FAIRification of the SSH. The blog will help to foment the discussion of such issues, give examples of FAIR implementations, and describe good practices. Given the amount of time required for this work, the project will be taken over by the CO-OPERAS IN team.

V. Recommendations and next steps

A. Recommendations

In conclusion, the various studies and activities conducted throughout the task confirmed that the SSH are currently in a transitional period as far as the FAIR principles are concerned. On the one hand, the domain has specificities related to well-rooted practices which do not always match the genericity that the FAIR principles imply. On the other hand, even when considering fields fully integrated with the digital environment, like digital humanities, the knowledge about the FAIR principles' content and purpose remains often scarce. More generally, in order to expand the FAIR principles' adoption within the

SSH, it is the principles' finality that should be outlined, showing how they increase the quality of research and can integrate even convergent, although pre-existing, practices.

Generally speaking, further actions should therefore be planned, taking into account three main aspects: advocacy, contextualization, and coordination. The effort to advocate for the FAIR principles started within the task should be sustained through the CO-OPERAS IN and, more largely, through the OPERAS RI. The specificities of SSH in terms of data types, dissemination infrastructures, existing curation practices should be preserved through the FAIR principles' contextualization. The SSH fragmented landscape and the variety of its objects will, furthermore, require coordinated actions of the various actors in the field, closely connecting the SSH infrastructures between themselves and with the research communities.

More specifically, all the above can be summarized through the following list of recommendations, grouped by the type of actors involved:

For Research Infrastructures and Researchers:

- 1. Research Infrastructures implementing FAIR should consider the research communities needs in order to align the implementation with the research practices and finalities.**
- 2. Specificities of the SSH in terms of digital objects, non-digital sources, scientific methods, and curation activities should be preserved and transposed into adapted FAIR implementations.**
- 3. An inventory of existing FAIRification tools should be provided and enriched with new tools dedicated to SSH specific objects, such as publications or cultural heritage materials.**
- 4. The FAIRification of dissemination and discovery services should preserve the multilingualism and bibliodiversity of the SSH environment.**

For Researchers:

- 5. Communities should collaborate on common minimal metadata sets allowing for cross-disciplinary research and the building of FAIR digital objects.**

For Research Infrastructures:

6. **Advocacy for the adoption of FAIR principles should be expanded offering both explanations on the FAIR principles and examples of FAIR tools and services.**
7. **Training dedicated to FAIR data and metadata should be provided to the SSH research communities, considering the disciplines, data types, and existing standards specificities.**
8. **The FAIRification of data and services should also address sustainability in order to fully ensure reuse in the longer term.**
9. **SSH infrastructures and projects involved in the FAIRification should coordinate with each other in order to offer consistent guidance to their respective communities.**

For Funders and Policy makers:

10. **Openly sharing data and publications and conforming them to the FAIR principles should be better recognized and rewarded.**

As can be seen, while many recommendations concern a specific type of actor, we put in the first place the recommendation involving both researchers and Research Infrastructures, to remind us that the FAIRification effort will necessarily be a collective and collaborative one. Furthermore, this first group of recommendations concerns more broadly the research community, including librarians and publishers. More specific recommendations regard the researchers' involvement, but also funders and institutions and their existing reward system. Finally, the recommendations also highlight that a major effort is required from the Research Infrastructures themselves in order to facilitate the transition towards a FAIR ecosystem for the SSH.

B. Next steps

As mentioned above, a few next actions have been already identified within the OPERAS-P task and, where necessary, will be taken over by the OPERAS RI and the CO-OPERAS IN. Here is a list of the main expected outcomes of OPERAS activities regarding the FAIRification of SSH data and publications:

- **Advocacy**

Communication material dedicated to FAIR is being created within the OPERAS SIG on advocacy. Printable cards will present the main aspects, objectives, and benefits of FAIRification.

- **Training**

Training activities are also envisioned through a collaboration between OPERAS, OpenAire, and the EOSC-Pillar project. The objective is to organize workshops or webinars for researchers focused on both a general presentation of the FAIR principles and descriptions of FAIR-enabling tools. The training could therefore be dedicated to specific disciplines or objects.

- **Support**

The task already allowed us to draft a FAIR publishing toolkit based on the FAIRification of OpenEdition. The objective is to provide open access publishers with online step-by-step documentation about the FAIRification of their services. The next step is therefore to finalize the toolkit through collaboration with other open access publishing platforms and building on existing toolkits (e.g., the Cessda's Data Management Expert Guide¹⁰ or the DOAB's OA books toolkit¹¹).

- **Communication**

A common space of discussion for the SSH community will be open thanks to a blog dedicated to the FAIR SSH. The blog will allow discussing FAIRification aspects in the SSH, present FAIR tools, methods, and implementations, and inform on related news and events. The blog will also give the opportunity for the community to discuss the best way to increase the FAIRness level and visibility, for instance by creating a dedicated journal.

- **Implementation**

To foster FAIR implementation in the various SSH areas, it is also planned to further

¹⁰ <https://www.cessda.eu/Training/Training-Resources/Library/Data-Management-Expert-Guide>.

¹¹ <https://www.oabooks-toolkit.org/>.

improve the SSH Implementation Profiles. It will require active engagement with the communities in order to make these profiles actually useful and usable by the various actors of such communities, especially by expanding the list of suggested examples.

- **Coordination**

At a broader level, a closer collaboration about the SSH FAIRification should bring together OPERAS, the ERICs for SSH Cessda, CLARIN, and DARIAH, as well as projects such as SSHOC and EOSC-Pillar. More precisely, notably in the context of FAIR Digital Objects implementations, coordinated action will have to better connect individual repositories and domain aggregators, like for instance SSHOC or TRIPLE.

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2019:

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Turin: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3999349>

Coimbra: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3999357>

2020:

Göttingen: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3999330>

Paris: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3999351>

Brussels (international): <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3999359>

C. List of disciplines represented in the workshops

Archaeology

Archives (Art history)

Botany

Chemistry

Classical studies (Latin literature)

Communication Science

Compared literature

Cultural Heritage

Digital Humanities

Economy

Ethnology

French literature

Hindology

History

History of Philosophy

International Law

Library and Information Science

Linguistics

Literature

Musicology
 Philology
 Philosophy
 Portuguese Studies
 Sociology

D. SSH Implementation Profile draft

Principle	Question	FAIR resources	Examples
Findability			
F1	What globally unique, persistent, resolvable identifiers do you use for metadata records?	Identifier type	DOI
F1	What globally unique, persistent, resolvable identifiers do you use for datasets?	Identifier type	Handle.net
F2	Which metadata schemas do you use for findability?	Metadata schema	DublinCore, CMDI
F3	What is the technology that links the persistent identifiers of your data to the metadata description?	Metadata-Data linking mechanism	Linked Open Data
F4	In which search engines are your metadata records indexed?	Search engines	VLO, OpenAIRE
F4	In which search engines are your datasets indexed?	Search engines	Datcite
Accessibility			
A1.1	Which standardized communication protocol do you use for metadata records?	Communication protocol	OAI-PMH, SPARQL
A1.1	Which standardized communication protocol do you use for datasets?	Communication protocol	HTTP REST API
A1.2	Which authentication & authorisation technique do you use for metadata	Authentication & authorisation technique	EGI check-in

	records?		
A1.2	Which authentication & authorisation technique do you use for datasets?	Authentication & authorisation technique	eduGAIN, ORCID
A2	Which metadata longevity plan do you use?	Metadata longevity	CoreTrustSeal
Interoperability			
I1	Which knowledge representation languages (allowing machine interoperation) do you use for metadata and/or datasets?	Knowledge representation language	XML, RDF
I2	Which structured vocabularies do you use to annotate your metadata records?	Structured vocabularies	LCSH, Thesaurus for Social Sciences
I3	Which models, schema(s) do you use for your metadata records?	Metadata schema	Dublin Core, schema.org
I3	Which models, schema(s) do you use for your datasets?	Data schema	Data Documentation Initiative
Reusability			
R1.1	Which usage license do you use for your metadata records?	Data usage license	Creative Commons 0 waiver
R1.1	Which usage license do you use for your datasets?	Data usage license	CC-BY, Apache
R1.2	Which metadata schemas do you use for describing the provenance of your metadata records?	Provenance model	W3C Provenance Ontology
R1.2	Which metadata schemas do you use for describing the provenance of your datasets?	Provenance model	Data Documentation Initiative
<p>This Implementation Profile is an adapted version of the FAIR Implementation Profile mini-questionnaire created by the GOFAIR Coordination office.</p>			

E. Example of the FAIR assessment grid used by OpenEdition

FAIR assessment of OpenEdition journal data			
Data summary			
Data sources	Data produced through Lodel by publishers and users Can be updated (not fully controlled by the organization) Documentary units' distinct levels: text, issue and collection levels		
Data expressions	Raw data: Lodel database (as used for the HTML expression) Other expressions: TEI OpenEdition, PDF, ePUB Metadata		
Commentary	<p>Different properties depending on the type (proper to Lodel software):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Volume contains: Publications (issues, columns, annual columns); Documentary unit contains texts, - Different types of texts (article, column, editorial, review, ...), - Annexed files types can contain data (xls, csv, sound, image, video files), <p>Not all the different types are available in all the different expressions (TEI, pdf, epub)</p> <p>Question: Should the review consider the types that do not correspond to specific content (subpart, section, site, directory, etc.)?</p>		
	FAIR implementations	FAIR enabling information	FAIR limitations
Findable			
F1. (Meta)data are assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier	Objects: - DOI (prefix 10.4000): available only for some data (depending on the types and publishers' wishes)	- OAI identifiers exist for all documentary units but are not PIDs - All documentary units are identified in the information system though	Objects: - Some data without any PID - DOIs may exist for data published on another platform that we do not retrieve.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Issue for resources with multiple DOIs - Handles generated by the Isidore harvesting platform (not retrieved by OE) <p>Persons: few Orcid IDs</p> <p>Organizations: few IDs from the Crossref Funding registry.</p>	<p>the concatenation: Platform+SiteName+ID</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Handles assigned by Isidore are not retrieved. <p>Persons: Contributors are not linked to registries.</p>
F2. Data are described with rich metadata (defined by R1 below)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Metadata available in the OAI-PMH repository (could be richer) - Formats DublinCore, DublinCoreTerms, METS 	<p>Rich metadata available; could be extensively integrated in the OAI repository.</p> <p>In OAI, metadata available only for certain types (subpart, heading, and news are missing)</p>	
F3. Metadata clearly and explicitly include the identifier of the data they describe	<p>In the OAI repository:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ID OAI - DOI when available 		Some data without any PID (see F1)
F4. (Meta)data are registered or indexed in a searchable resource	<p>OpenEdition Search interface (search.openedition.org):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - only a selection of data is available (some types are excluded), - metadata are not complete. <p>(Meta)data is also searchable in other directories (for example,</p>	<p>No public API available yet, but all the information is available through the search software (SolR)</p>	

	Isidore harvests OE's OAI repository)		
Accessible			
A1. (Meta)data are retrievable by their identifier using a standardised communications protocol	HTML: accessible via the DOI Metadata: accessible via the OAI identifier		Some data without any PID (see F1)
A1.1 The protocol is open, free, and universally implementable	HTTP for the data OAI-PMH for the metadata		
A1.2 The protocol allows for an authentication and authorisation procedure, where necessary	All protocols are open, but not all allow for authentication. Protocol used for restricted access contents: - TCP/IP for contents requiring authentication (the TEI version case) Other protocols used where authentication is not required: - HTTP for the open access content - OAI-PMH for the metadata		Lack of a tool dedicated to the management of authentication and authorization processes.
A2. Metadata are accessible, even when the data are no longer available	No		No records for the deleted data.
Interoperable			

I1. (Meta)data use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation.	TEI, DC, METS		No semantic layer is implemented.
I2. (Meta)data use vocabularies that follow FAIR principles	In some journals, use of disciplinary controlled vocabularies (such as French Pactols).	Some disciplinary controlled vocabularies (JEL, GeographieUN) could be integrated with thesaurus management tools	For most journals, no controlled vocabulary is used.
I3. (Meta)data include qualified references to other (meta)data	In OAI repository: - is part of - relation with OpenAIRE accessright field Some links with translations	- Citation and Cited-by available but not disseminated - Link with translations not recorded in the OAI repository - on-going project: OE Review of Books	
Reusable			
R1.1. (Meta)data are released with a clear and accessible data usage license	Licenses are defined by journals and not by documentary units, except in a few cases. The license is not defined according to the different expressions, the same licence applies for all.	License should be distinct for each expression and the information be added to the database and the TEI	No clear provision to allow for the text and data mining exception (acknowledged by French law “Loi pour une république numérique”) The license applied to the documents is not always clear.

			The license has sometimes been declared by the journal retroactively, and has therefore an uncertain value.
R1.2. (Meta)data are associated with detailed provenance	Internal creation process not described (can be created through Lodel, outsourced digitization, etc.)		
R1.3. (Meta)data meet domain-relevant community standards	I1: (meta)data meet community standards for textual contents, including TEI. I2: Fewer (meta)data meet disciplinary communities standards.		

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